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**The dynamics of Higher Education in Mozambique and Interplay
with the Working Market: The contribution of Engineering,
Humanities and Social Sciences**

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ABSTRACT

The empirical data from Mozambique where HE has quickly grown since the mid-1990s over the liberalization of the market is instigating concerns on the linkages between universities and the industry. Drawing from a tracey Methodology of Mozambican graduates in two universities, Eduardo Mondlane University (UEM) and Pedagogical University (UP) in the domains of Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities, this article embarks on investigating the contribution HE made to the Mozambique labor market (between 1970s to 2000s). In so doing, the paper shows that tracey studies as a research method that accounts for relevance of HE has been severely neglected in the country. In exploring such new method this research brings a new unit of analysis based on two embryonic notions namely that despite public debate developing the view that the surge of graduations leads to unemployment, in Mozambique there are fluctuations in terms of institution of instruction, field of specialization and period graduates enrolled in HE. Secondly, there has been a dominant misconception of viewing universities solely as channels for employability rather than paragons where cultivation of knowledge, culture and skills necessary for adjustment in different contexts of life are nurtured. The rapid growth of Social Sciences & Humanities and devaluation of engineering skills within universities in Mozambique sustains all these views.

Key Words: HE, fields of knowledge, employability, Mozambique. Engineering

Review of Literature: Contribution of knowledge universities generate to society and implications

International analyses on the expansion of HE (see Teichler, 2005:453 and Tight, 2012: 279) have increasingly urged for a looming prediction of university crisis since the 1970s. During this period, the public debate instigated investigations on the effects of rapid growth and inflation of HE with focus for future employment as a result of the highest number of graduates terminating university. The case of Mozambique's establishment of HE shows an apparent contradiction in terms of rise of university and concerns of future unemployment nexus. There are several approaches for such delink on the interplay between the inception and development of high learning in either Africa or elsewhere and concerns on the absorption of the graduates by the industry. In Africa the focus on engineering skills has been less emphasized and minimization of practical problems affecting the country prevail as a result.

The international scrutiny of universities based on employability and application of the abilities Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) confer to the graduates; (see Tight, 2012) show changing relationships between universities and the industry. In addition, the employing market has now shifted priorities from humanities and social skills to concentrate on engineering abilities contradicting the long held type of investment African states made on social sciences and humanities. Still in SSA the landscape interlinking skills and development reveals the dominance of a kind of university that less addresses the need for engineers on one hand and overwhelming existence of social scientists on the other.

These drifting contradictions confirm the loom of new themes that dominate the public debate on the interpretation of HE's meaning. In this sense the link between expansion of HE, work and skills can be interpreted as a phenomenon that belongs to a field of its own, which is research in HE. Internationally, the necessity of linking universities, skills acquisition and application through employment has been evidenced by riots emerging in the 1960s, which led both national and regional states to address participation, expansion and inclusion in HE as indexes that influence solutions to practical problems when approached from the theoretical and empirical perspectives uniquely to high learning.

Furthermore, the swift of concentration to focus on market management in the 1980s as a new theme implied new strategies of governance in HE whereas internationalization and globalization in the 1990s have accelerated investigations of proximities between universities to become modern institutions where generation of knowledge and applicability interconnect. The definition of skills that contribute to minimization of national problems has been in this perspective allied with dominant topics when in Africa theoretical and empirical evidence did not match. The approach idealized by Tight (2012) on the importance of current themes as a starting position to address the way universities operate complies with Teichler (2005) empirical data about the description of the abruptness of enrollment rates, graduations and employment nexus debate. In the context of Germany envisaged by Teichler (2005), for instance, university-based centers were popularized within universities as means of interlinking relevance of knowledge that became produced and applicability in the labor market, always aligning this with the quick rise of university graduates (Teichler, 2005: 455).

It is then undoubted that the correlation between universities, state and industry have since constituted international debates and curricular adjustments that aligned with the dynamics of labor market occur/red. However, even though this level of analysis (international) may be deemed as universal considering the perspective of inheritance of the Western university that spread across the African continent (including in Mozambique), concrete concerns on the theme university-employment-practical skills remains predominantly shaped by either national or regional levels under which particular higher education systems operate apart from contextual approaches.

Analyzing the national context of Mozambique, the linkages between universities, knowledge and applicability of such knowledge in the industry is meriting both cautious and systematic research. Consequently, even though the system in itself remains elitist (see Author, 2016: 27) as only about 3% of the population aged to go to university have access, a case common with other contexts of similar GDP as Mozambique, research is evidencing a unique feature of the latter country's HE. The nation is characterized by existence of exclusive shifts on the relationship between graduates and employability and the magnitude of disproportionality is considerably surging only in the last decade (2010s). Historical perspectives on the genesis of university in Mozambique may explain some of these paradoxes, especially the predominance of social sciences and humanities versus marginalization of engineering courses.

When the Mozambican HE awakened in 1962, the character of universities remained that of selecting and instructing the dominant Portuguese elites. The public debate on the role of HE for labor force prevailed undebatable as a result and the need for practical skills was less emphasized. There are at least two reasons that explained such perspective. Primarily (a) is the fact that the function of university was not mainly that of nurturing the industry but was explained in terms of both instigation and establishment of distinctive groups of citizens namely the knowledgeable (Portuguese) and the unknowledgeable (indigenous Mozambican). In the international level both Castells (2001) and Rothblatt (1997) described this approach in terms of generation of science for its own sake. In addition, (b) the notion of university versus formal employability in the context of Mozambique was novel not excluding the fact that such interlink lacked competitors as only one Mozambican graduated from university at this period. The emergence of HE in Mozambique instigated theoretical skills rather than empirical abilities.

Immediately after independence between 1976 and 1995 the state remained the unique provider of HE in Mozambique, it both steered and legislated the public universities that dominated the country. It also focused on social sciences and humanities given there was no sufficient funds to invest on practical courses. As a result, there was a stable correlation and interplay between universities and relevance through direct applicability of the knowledge that HEIs conferred to the industry based on the graduates. However, the liberalization of the market that followed subsequently in the context of Mozambique apparently confirmed the paragon of the demise that university graduation and employment are necessarily interconnected. There are visible empirical factors that contributed for this when investigating the growth of Mozambican system of high learning. The surge of private HEIs associated with the increasing number of graduates that terminated university after this period incremented lack of optimism on universities for those who solely regarded either access to HE as a success or guarantee for job. A quick survey on the stages of Mozambican HE growth as indicated, in terms of universities, enrolments and graduations may account for the complexity of the above captioned inconsistencies between access to university and

value of the science universities generated as industry emerged and integration became competitive.

Table 1: Historical emergence of universities, enrolment and graduations: earlier connections with the industry and arena of specialization

Period	Nr. of Institutions	Average inputs	Average Outputs
1962-1975	1	500	400
1976-1995	3	1000	900
1996-2016	50	10000	8500

Source: Interpretation of Mozambican HE Expansion and Graduations

The three categories indicated in table 1 above account for the overall landscape of the rapid expansion of the Mozambican HE system with both institutions and inputs surging abruptly in the last period of analyses (1996-2016). However, such growth has been less visible in engineering as it dominated social sciences and humanities. Given the focus is to interpret the correlation between the contribution of two universities to the industry and map the gap existing between graduations and employment based on tracey study of the graduates from Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities, the notion of an existing delink between university expansion and work force suggests an indigenous analyses of university rise. Graph 2 pictures the empirical evidence about the rise of participation in higher education in Mozambique in compliance with the domains set to be analyzed.

Graph 2: Selection of the courses and average participation in higher education (graduations and interconnection with the work market).

Source (interpretation of statistical data on higher education expansion in Mozambique & Uetela 2017: 22).

Despite the gradual rise of participation in HE for the categories selected as the main domains that interlinked universities with the industry (between the 1970s and 2010s) through knowledge production, variations in these fields of professions may outstand. In addressing this perspective, the global context's research in HE has strongly indicated the necessity of understanding both cultures of knowledge production and levels at which such nurturing or cultivation of tribes concerning knowledge occur (see. Jawitz, 2009; Jones 2009; Healy, 2005; Henkel, 2005; Maassen, & Cloete, 2002;

Neumann and Becher, 2002 and Tight, 2012) in order to enable assessment of the way universities generate skills that influence the industry.

Hence, along with cultures and levels of analyses the dominant themes of interest for the researchers above captioned became identities, autonomy, policy, communities, attributes, contexts, tribes of knowledge and field. All these categories comply to the concern that the way Social Sciences, Humanities and Engineering are structured to influence the industry in the context of Mozambique is shaped by international analyses though the national level dominates the magnitude at which graduates' expertise contribute to the economy.

The analyses about the contribution of the universities to the industry may not solely be limited to the increasingly growing communities of knowledge generation as it may contradict this study considering it was based on 3 cultures from where the graduates became traced. However, it is also linked to what Gibbons et al (1994), Gornitzka (2008) and Gumpert (2000) consider as the consequences of the global dynamics that are driven by shifts in institutional arrangements which even though maintain borders of knowledge the interconnection between universities, the state and the market have sharply been delinked.

Definition of Methodology: Tracing graduates from Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities courses at UEM and UP in Mozambique

The differentiation between Engineering, Social sciences and humanities especially measured by employability and acquisition of skills that are relevant to solve practical problems has been less debated in Mozambican HE despite universities being sites where systematic knowledge and practical problem solving is constructed. Assessing how graduates become employed in compliance with the knowledge obtained in HE (Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities) may suggest a new approach of both teaching Engineering skills within Mozambican universities and lessen their marginalization.

Based on academic registration of the universities selected, this study sampled from 1913 students that graduated in engineering between 1970s to 2010s (see table 2) distributed in averages accordingly (1970s:0 graduates; 1980s-1990s: 348 graduates; 2000s: 578 and 2010s: 987). A scale of 5 was applied (1913:5) as a means to determine the representative sample of the engineers who graduated from UEM over the period the study covered (382 engineers) and then traced those.

In terms of Social Sciences and Humanities, the above referenced strategy was also applied though with a sharp reconfiguration in the latter professions given the significant differences in terms of statistics presented between fields of specialization. For the Social Sciences and Humanities as also shown in table 3 the average distribution over the period under investigation is as follow (1970s: 1 graduate; 1980s and 1990s: 1103 graduates; 2000s: 3017 graduates and 2010s: 6475 graduations). Therefore, out of the 10596 total graduates from the domains (Social Sciences and Humanities) a scale of 10 was defined in order to trace 1.059 workers (graduates).

Under this strategy table 2 bellow shows how sampling exercise for following up (to trace graduates) was determined in the fields of knowledge production and universities selected. In addition, table 3 subsequently accounts for the structure of the questionnaire applied for interviews and the results obtained which place Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities at different stages.

Table 3: Sampling strategy and definition of tracey study for the Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities at UEM and UP

Selected Field	University	Total graduates	of Total of sample and scale
Engineering	UEM	1913	1913:5=382.6 graduates
Social Sciences & H.	UP	10596	10596:10=1059.6 graduates

Source: Data interpretation

Table 4: Structure of the questionnaire applied for follow up and outcome from the informants

1. Gender	Percentage of respondents
(a) Male	75%
(b) Female	25%
Total	100%
2. Age range of the respondents	
(a) 24-years old	7%
(b) 27-years old	7%
(c) 28-years old	7%
(d) 29-years old	12,75%
(e) 30-years old	12,75%
(f) 32-years old	7%
(g) 33-years old	12,75%
(h) 34-years old	7%
(i) 35-years old	7%
(j) 36-years old	7%
(k) 38-years old	12,75%
Total	100%
3. When did you graduate? (Social Sciences, Humanities & Engineering)	
(a) 1999	5,25%
(b) 2003	5,25%q
(c) 2005	10,50%
(d) 2006	26,25%
(e) 2008	5,25%
(f) 2009	5,25%
(g) 2010	5,25%
(h) 2011	16%
(i) 2012	5,25%
(j) 2013	5,25%
(k) 2014	5,25%
(l) 2015	5,25%
4. What course did you attend?	
(1) Engineering	16,00%
(2) Social Sciences and Humanities	84,00%

5. When did you start looking for a paid job?	
(a) Before University	30%
(b) During University	10%
(c) After University	55%
(d) Did not seek for job	5%
For those whose answer was (c) in the previous question (obtained the job after graduation) how long did it take you to obtain a paid work after terminating HE?	
(1) 0 to 3 months	50%
(2) 4 to 6 months	18,70%
(3) 7 to 9 months	0%
(4) 10 to 12 months	0%
(5) more than a year	31,30%
6. Considering your job and activities, to what extent do you apply the skills and knowledge conferred to you by the university?	
(1) Always	50%
(2) To a greater extent	35%
(3) To some extent	10%
(4) Rarely	5%
(5) I do not use	0%
7. To what extent does your job correspond to the area of specialization?	
(1) Perfectly	20%
(2) To a greater extent	30%
(3) To some extent	20%
(4) Thinly	15%
(5) Does not at all	15%
8. Did university participation meet the expectations you had before attending HE?	
(1) Perfectly	20%
(2) To a greater extent	25%
(3) To some extent	35%
(4) Thinly meets	5%
(5) Does not at all	15%
9. Based on your experience, would you recommend someone to go to university?	
(a) Yes	95,20%
(b) No	4,80%

Discussion

The context of Mozambican alignment between expansion of HE and application of Engineering, social sciences and humanity skills through employment drawn from the data above described confirms the theory that national levels of analyses are important and shape specific HE subsystems. The description of the contribution of the industry to the Mozambican economy over the period analyzed becomes interesting to address the share of Engineering and the new approach universities should make to teach practical skills in order to solve practical problems. From the statistics, the specialization of graduates selected show variations in terms of contribution each arena of knowledge production makes to the economy of Mozambique as the study by Balchin et al (2017) over a 2-decade period further evidences on the link between skills and growth of the economy in the country.

Graph 3: Contribution of the sectors of the economy where graduates of Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities might be employed.

Source: Interpretation of Balchin et al (2017: 16) versus data from the follow up of the graduates

Results and Conclusions

HE in Mozambique has emerged rapidly since its inception in indigenous context in the 1970s though a considerable growth of both universities and graduations significantly increased in the mid-1990s overall. The fact led to new concerns on the link between universities and work turning into a public debate since the 2010s, the moment the number of graduates in Social Sciences and Humanities surged abruptly. Furthermore, whereas in the international context both research on HE and reflections on the consequences of the growing statistics of graduates that finished university became a popular dispute in the late 1970s (cf. Tight, 2012 and Teichler, 2005), the case of Mozambique features a national analysis of its unique conceptualization.

Universities in Mozambique remain the modern spotlights that instigate transformation through informed knowledge and have since their inception maintained dominance in preparing and impacting skills that are necessary for the workforce (Castells, 2001) extending this to the generation of systematic knowledge, instruction of the human capital and dominant elites in societies. However, this did not occur at same level in all arenas of knowledge production. The actual concerns on the misalignment between graduations and labor in Mozambique evidences that there has been less emphasizes on teaching Engineering skills as theoretical problems rather than practical have dominated since.

The case of Mozambique remains unique and merits a local level analysis in the sense that despite growing interest on matching expansion of HE and work, research is showing high levels of misrepresentation of engineers in a period where practical skills for practical problem resolution is relevant. Universities are both meaningful and important institutions as informants from both engineering, social sciences and humanities urge other clients to be part (cf. 95, 20% of respondents who support the role of university

and informed knowledge in enhancing transformation) to the extent of yearning others to enroll.

The assessment of university relevance and meaning based on the interplay between access and acquisition of skills for work, show variations for the specific case of Mozambique. Whereas the majority consent to have acquired a paid job in the first 3 months after graduations (50% of the informants) there is also a reasonable number of graduates who remain unemployed for at least more than a year (30% of respondents). These statistics indicate that even though overall analyses of the meaning of universities show a correlation between graduations and work (the 50%) which contradicts the other perspective that growing enrollments lead to unemployment (the 30% unemployed graduates within a minimum of one year period), may sustain the contradictory functions under which Engineering and social sciences are mingled in within Mozambique. There are at least 3 perspectives of analyses that impact on the variations of the results from this research in terms of either relevance or irrelevance of universities reproducing the skills acquired in Engineering and social sciences disciplines which are essential for job attainment and contribution to the economy.

The placement of the universities selected (UEM and UP) and the courses analyzed in terms of (Social Sciences and Humanities) do not feature at the same level that foster equilibrium on the results. Again, the cultures of knowledge and institutional analyses (Neuman, 2002 and Tight, 2012 respectively) can be recalled to describe the Mozambican HE, which suggests that institutions and vocations are also key elements in linking graduations with employment. UEM and the profession of Engineering are both highly ranked and with few graduates respectively. Hypothetically, this fact led to quick integration in the labor market though the share for the growth of the economy and solution of practical problems remains low. The approach of elicitation of both institutions and graduations contradicts the dominant discourse that rising numbers of graduates going to university has led to unemployment if one considers this empirical evidence. Furthermore, the case of 50% respondents who quickly acquired employability, confirms the theory access to university versus employment nexus as correlated.

On contrary perspective, the case of UP (Social Sciences and Humanities) shows a different evidence as compared to UEM and Engineering. In the latter case both enrollments and graduations have considerably grown faster. Consequently, the theory of disconnection between universities and employment may comply to the situation of UP where surge of graduations in Social sciences and humanities has led to disproportionalities between graduates and job opportunities. The case of 30% statistics pointing to the integration after one year might characterize specific contexts of the majority of universities with specializations that alike the Pedagogic University have invested in domains of knowledge production that became popularized rather than elicited as is the case of Engineering.

The antagonistic and descriptive concerns on the landscape of the Mozambican context in terms of the link between universities and employment imposes the necessity of a cautious and analytical approach based on both contextual and national analyses in order to lessen prejudices that the rapid growth in graduation rates has always led to unemployment of the participants in HE. Instead, based on the fields of specialization analyzed, whereas in some contexts rapid expansion and graduation rates have resulted in cultivation of skills that foster knowledge culture essential for solution of

practical problems in the industry, the case of domains of knowledge production that became popular has driven to unemployment (Engineering versus Social Sciences and Humanities) respectively.

The second perspective is associated with the periodicity in which such domains of knowledge production either emerged or developed. Though at the beginning (1970s and 1980s) both Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities were at the initial stage, the role of universities at this moment in Mozambique was not necessarily employment. Preferably, the mission of HE remained that of producing knowledge that was relevant to strengthen public institutions that turned weakened after the colonial drift. During the liberalization of the economy in the 1990s there was a swift predominance in deeming universities as the modern institutions that instigate the link between knowledge and work allied with the inception of new markets.

The analyses of Mozambique's interconnections between graduations and work based on the second perspective above suggest that not only institutional, arenas of knowledge production and periodical developments of HE are essential but also historical perspectives and dynamics of ideologies have affected the interplay between expansion of HE and the popular disputes for engineering and social sciences. The fact that some graduates affirm to have looked for jobs either before or during university studies suggests that employability is not necessarily aligned with participation in HE or university certificate. Thus, formal employment is viewed by the majority of the informants to be conferred by universities given that a significant percentage (55%) did not seek job before HE completion. This approach shows that the dominant misconception that universities have the role of mainly preparing professionals for work is not solely a public concern but it also shapes the categories of reasoning internalized by key participants in HE (the graduates themselves). In addition, the case of engagement in jobs before and during university participation considered as part-time occupations that guarantee subsistence while waiting for the standardized appointment conferred after university further sustains the major vision of university in providing employability independent of the arena of expertise.

The third element that emerges is the role of the state that remained insufficient in both steering public HE allowing the insurgence of private universities a case which increased graduations in social sciences and humanities and lessened the capacities of Engineering. The historical development of Mozambican HE as prescribed by the empirical data presented in this research accounts for a surge of both universities and graduations only after the 1990s when liberalization of the economy became emphasized with individual institutions also preparing graduates for the labor force. This fact is revealed by the growing statistics in the fields of Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities both at UEM and UP from this period. Considering these universities and their arenas/cultures of knowledge production are ancient as compared to other institutions and domains, the demise of the correlation between graduations versus employment might be high at other universities that remain novel and the industry has been sharply reluctant in admitting their labor force/capitals.

The fact that the state has shifted priorities both as a provider and steering force of HE in the context of Mozambique, has incremented unbalance between universities, courses offered and employment. This is a contradiction in a context characterized by access to higher education that remains considerably elitist (3% of participation). In the international perspectives where the public debate on increasing

graduations versus unemployment emerged, the discussion has been associated with the fact that their systems were moving towards universalization of access in all knowledge disciplines (above 45%) as Trow (1970) describes.

In Mozambique at least 7 economic sectors feature as the main participating powers to the growth of the economy through GDP overall categorized in terms of (i) Agriculture, (ii) Mining and Utilities, (iii) Manufacturing, (iv) Construction, (v) Wholesale, Retail & Hotels, (vi) Transport, Storage & Communication and (vii) Other. The influence of these sectors to the growth of the economy of the country suggests that there has been an increasing demand and reliance on knowledge produced in social sciences and humanities and transformation of the country then moved slowly. Given that universities have become the new paragons where various actors interconnect to select relevant knowledge and culture (see Delanty, 2002) the predominance of the 7 above captioned sectors that influence growth in Mozambique impose a necessary interconnection between universities and growth of the national state at least in terms of systematic knowledge and utility nexus.

Such findings, which contradict the concept of demise of universities that dominated Africa and the role they play for societal and cultural change in Mozambique comply with the public debate that the notion of knowledge age is driving across national and regional perspectives. Therefore, the need for reinvention of universities not only as the institutions that guarantee employability but also where relevant knowledge for application at different contexts features as the new model that will shape curricula and definition of the meaning of university in the case of Mozambique.

An outstanding question arises based on the data from this country imposing a reflection on how universities can maximize relevance and continuity of their existence in a period where the delink between surging graduations in Social Sciences and Humanities versus employability since the 2000s is leading to high levels of contestation and demise of HEIs. Consequently, a threefold measure recommendation outstands for the case of Mozambique as a means to maximize the relationship between universities, work and skills that Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities offer. Firstly, there is a need to restructure curricula in the courses selected for follow up (Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities) in compliance with the market. The alignment shown in the data between the area of specialization and the current job of the graduates represented by 20%, 30%, 20% and 15% totalizing 85% imposes reforms on curricula of the specializations sampled. Despite existence of variations in levels of correspondence only 15% of informants showed disconnection between the field of instruction and arena of employability, an approach mapping the prevalence of the notion that specific skills and expertise will lead to specific jobs on one hand. However, on the other hand statistics show that the way under which markets operate is dynamic and predicted jobs are eroding. Hence, the need for curricula structure which, fosters skills that are transferable to different contexts of application and employability including self-employment becomes indispensable for university not only in Engineering courses, but in many other domains of knowledge generation.

Secondly, the meaning of university should shift from the view of promoting public good to the notion of private benefits (see Gumport, 2000) in a sense that the attachment between access to university and employability promoted by the state in terms of public interest is sharply reducing in the country. Even though it appears as a contradiction to foster private benefits in situations where universities play a public role, the state at

which a necessary correlation between graduation and employability is slightly decreasing in Mozambique, imposes a cultivation of new abilities on participants of high learning. Those are not based solely on disciplinary contexts (pure Engineering, Social Sciences and Humanities). Instead, new notions need to be integrated within disciplinary cultures focusing on heterogeneity of knowledge, interdisciplinarity, multidisciplinary or even interinstitutionalization (see Gibbons, 1994). This novel drift will enable that even in cases where the growing number of specialists (Social Sciences and Humanities) that their integration in the industry occurs after at least one year, the new abilities based on multiversity (see Rothblatt, 1997) will foster integration in dynamic perspectives of the markets especially through maximization of graduates' own employability. The perspective leads to the last analysis and attempt to respond to the quest of growing unbalance between graduations, knowledge domains and employability in the perspective discussed for the context of Mozambique, which is associated with the decrease of influence on the role of the state.

Consequently, research in HE and data analyses drawn from this investigation reveal a sharp delink between the triple-helix's main stakeholders of HE in Mozambique viewed in the global context as pivotal to instigate success based on the way universities should operate (cf. Clark, 1983). The case of Engineering in Mozambique suggests that the applicability of the previous two looming notions of interlinking rapid growth of graduations versus employability is only possible through nurturing a strong state that will invest on graduates' own employment and will bear with the risks of what is meant by entrepreneurship. Furthermore, the interplay between these three spotlights that will guarantee the success of the link between university outputs and integration in the labor market needs to be constantly strengthened. Such measure can be maximized through both informed and restructured curricula policy design so that the knowledge culture that is relevant for both self-employability and steer relevance of HE in the country based on the notion of knowledge society can be systematically cultivated through domains that are practical.

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